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Fides et Ratio: Faith & Philosophy

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Ramiro de Maeztu: The Philosophical Path to Conversion

By Enrique Sánchez Costa

Ramiro de Maeztu has been called the Spanish Chesterton, and for good reason. He was born in 1874, the same year as Chesterton, and was murdered in 1936, the year in which Chesterton died. He was, however, much more than merely Chesterton's exact contemporary. He was also, like Chesterton, a writer, journalist and man of letters who took the philosophical path to conversion, discovering faith through the exercise of reason. In this article, Enrique Sánchez Costa follows Maeztu's philosophical path.

Burning, burning, burning, burning
O Lord Thou pluckest me out
O Lord Thou pluckest
(*The Waste Land*, vv. 308–310).

“[A]mong the Spanish intellectuals of this century”, the American scholar I. Fox points out, “maybe José Ortega y Gasset and Miguel de Unamuno are the only ones who have surpassed, in intensity of thought and influence on socio-political currents, Ramiro de Maeztu.”¹ Dramatic witness of the progress and setbacks of the Europe that shaped the first third of the twentieth century, journalist *avant toute chose*, essayist and political thinker, Maeztu successively shifted from criticizing Spain in decline—that is why he was placed in the “generation of '98”—to defending “liberal socialism” and trade unionism (in his English period), before finally becoming anchored in traditionalism.

Unamuno depicts him as “a subtle and impressionable spirit, capable of being concerned with the most diverse problems, and

I think, not really able to be profoundly enamored of any cause for ever . . . a sybarite of the intelligence, that is, a man that has the full sensuality of concepts, doctrines, theories.”² The rector of Salamanca University captured Maeztu's perspicacity well and, at the same time, his tendency to variability, arising from his self-education and insatiable intellectual curiosity, which permeates his more than 4,000 published articles. However, his changing ideas did not prevent him from always being an active thinker, within the framework of political

Spiritually, he evolved from his youthful anticlericalism and weakly held faith to the increasing Catholicism of his maturity, which would eventually intermingle with his political ideas.

realism, attentive to the confirmation of events.

Spiritually, he evolved from his youthful anticlericalism and weakly-held faith to the increasing Catholicism of his maturity, which would eventually intermingle with his political ideas. Between the two poles was 1916: the year of the writer's conversion in London, at a time of lively ideological debate. And we speak of conversion (from the Hebrew words *šûb*, “go back” and “return”, and *naham*, “to repent”, brought

together in the Greek *μετάνοια*), since the semantic field of the latter is not limited to the idea of passing from one belief to another, but also includes “a radical transformation of the individual through participation in Christ's death and resurrection, that takes place in the Church as a community of faith.”³ This change or existential about-turn is thus carried out in Catholicism by following Christ—“we believe because we love”, said Newman; and, since faith is also dialogic, communal, it occurs within the Church: the family of God on earth.

Ramiro de Maeztu y Whitney—his mother was of an English family—was born in Vitoria (Basque Country) in 1874. He grew up happily, enjoying a careful, demanding upbringing. Not unnaturally, he received religious instruction: “I will never forget not only my first communion, but also my first years of mysticism.”⁴ To the unease of adolescence was added the bankruptcy of his father's business, which forced him to leave school and to seek employment, first in Paris, later in Cuba, where he performed dead-end jobs until his return in 1894 (the year of his father's death). Such misery was to embitter his nature, leading him to pessimism and a more caustic and combative attitude towards reality.

Working in the field of journalism, he soon became renowned in Madrid, making up the Group of Three together with Azorín and Baroja. The Cuban disaster in 1898 led these young intellectuals to fierce criticism of the Spain of the old school that had brought about such a tragedy. The

Church was soon to be a target of Maeztu's barbs: "Clericalism hinders Spanish economic development. . . . How beautiful it would be to unite wishes, now in disagreement, preparing them against the Church in the name of our daily bread!"⁵ He attacked the warped clerical mentality that preferred the extermination of liberals and press censorship to theological and evangelical work.

Despite his doubts and abandonment of religious observance, Maeztu did not revile Christian doctrine—"It is not the faith, but the landholders who are suffocating us";⁶ rather, he accused the "theocratic or ecclesiastical" oligarchy, together with other military and civil oligarchies, which were restricting Spanish progress. His regenerationist ideals rebelled at the thought that "the Spaniards of the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries had sacrificed the immediate interests of the motherland to the glory of God and the Church."⁷ In his despondency, he found an answer in Nietzsche—"the incomparable thinker"—the "German redeemer", who provided his remedy. On the basis of this discovery, a veritable gold mine, Maeztu was to invigorate the ideal of the regenerated man—the "messianic superman"—a believer in voluntarism—will to power—and militarism, and against estheticism, whose aristocratism or belief in the rule of high-brow elites was later to be developed by Ortega.

In politics, Maeztu set himself up as a "socialist" from 1897 to 1916. He considered that Spain had a "theocratic-plutocratic-landowner-bureaucratic regime, or that Spain was governed by the clergy, those wealthy in money, values and property, and the military and civil servants."⁸ He advocated subordinating the dominant oligarchies to the sovereignty of the law—whether in a Monarchy or Republic—just as the people are subject to the law. His socialism, which was evolving, became "administrative socialism", in which intellectuals and specialists should watch over its application for the benefit of the people. Having said that, he was not an advocate of doctrinaire socialism: he was independent and elitist,

detached from political parties; moreover, he rejected egalitarianism, man's natural goodness, and collective property.

In 1905 he moved to England as a newspaper correspondent. He was the first resident Spanish journalist in the City, where he went in pursuit of the secret of Anglo-Saxon political and economic superiority. It was between 1909 and 1911, while, together with Ortega, he judged culture as the lay fountain of "salvation", that his religious restlessness emerged. He wrote to the young Ortega: "I think your scorn (do I interpret you rightly?) of religiousness, which for me is the sensation of the

The doctrine of original sin—today at best provocative—does not refer to a hereditary personal fault, but to a disturbance of human nature, thus circumventing both Lutheran pessimism—which believes human nature to be rotten to the core—and the ingenuity of l'homme naturel, which does not satisfactorily elucidate the obvious presence of evil within the person.

Invisible, is very bad. Neither 20th century criticism, nor that of the 23rd [sic] century, can do anything against this feeling, which, now I realize, has always been in me and remains strong. It is the root of my life."⁹

This misty religiousness—"sensation of the Invisible"—that Maeztu wielded before Ortega was reinforced by his admiration of the Gospels: "What is said in them is what had to be said at every moment and what we would never have thought of". In this way, alongside the sublime nature of Jesus' words, he praised Jesus' power: "In his actions, however, not only is a power far superior to ours revealed, but also a disci-

pline or mastery of that power which make Jesus the best *professor of energy*, as used to be said thirty years ago."¹⁰ He was thus persuaded, "that the moral model for man ought to be sought in the *Gospels*."¹¹

As an intellectual alert to new ideas in London, a city undergoing perpetual transformation, he was to be in touch with different movements—such as the *Fabian Society*—networks, and friendships. The early influence of Baron von Hügel, who introduced him to his *London Society for the Study of Religion*, was to be particularly noticeable. The Baron, like Maeztu himself tall and self-taught, was friendly with both orthodox Catholic thinkers (Newman, W. Ward) and with modernist leaders (Loisy, Tyrrell, Fogazzaro). In his opinion, one finds God in action, in the world, at one's best moments and also by touching human finiteness. Hence, mysticism would not imply withdrawing from life, but experiencing the supernatural in the natural aspects of the world. Echoes of these ideas—and the interpretations that they gave rise to—resounded in an article of 1922, in which Maeztu attempted to "reconcile" worldly ideals with supernatural ones.

Nevertheless, this liberty is not given to us to deny the world, nor to run away, like Brandt, to an icy desert, not even for us to feel exiled and foreign to the world, as *Kempis* says, but to improve the world. . . . This world is the other world. The other world is this world in the fullness of its consequences. . . . That is why Maragall is right in his *Spiritual Canticle* when he is satisfied with this world. The other is this same world; yet our eyes will be able to see through it and to rest in God.¹²

From England he traveled to Germany to broaden his philosophical education. His first stay in Marburg in 1911 was to be a landmark in the development of his religious views. He discovered Hartmann's "realism" and glimpsed Husserl's phenomenology, which was developing at that time. As Millán-Puelles recalled with regard to the

introduction of European thought in Spain: “When Scheler was exercising true intellectual tyranny in Spain, the only voice that did Hartmann justice was Maeztu’s; besides, it brought us into contact with Anglo-Saxon thought.”¹³ Even so, his foremost discovery was to be Kant’s apriorism:

The most important event in my life was, conceivably, the joy that I felt on learning, in my study of the *Critique of Pure Reason*, of the existence of synthetic *a priori* judgments.¹⁴ . . . To Kant, whose philosophy I began to study in Germany in 1911, I owe the immutable underpinning of my religious thought. . . . He taught me precisely that the spirit cannot be derived from the non-spirit, . . . the very existence of synthetic *a priori* judgments, the fact that $2+2=4$ is a synthetic *a priori* judgment, that is, the fact that mathematics and logic are not, and cannot be, a reflection of material nature, but they are and have to be spiritual creation. When I realized this, I had to tell myself that the spirit is original, and not derived from matter.¹⁵

In this way, still aware that, as a whole, Kantian philosophy results in agnosticism, he adopted his criticism of empiricism (our singular and contingent experience cannot explain necessary universal judgments, which are prior to it) and his affirmation of the spirit, which for Maeztu was to signify the eternal and, ultimately, God. In the course of time, by means of the material ethic of Scheler’s and Hartmann’s values, G. E. Moore’s objective ethic, phenomenology and, above all, Maritain’s realism—knowledge does not fabricate its object: it tries to adapt itself to reality—Maeztu channeled and developed his initial interpretation of Kant. He was gradually to abandon Ortega’s perspectivism in order to penetrate faith, interest in which was to be revived by Unamuno: “the only Spaniard whom I am prepared to call my master”, of whom he asserted that “his best work is religious: *The Tragic Sense of Life*.”¹⁶

Once again in England, he was in touch

with *Guild Socialism*, a trade union movement that was averse to both Marxism and Fabian socialism, and whose platform of expression was the *New Age*. Edited from 1908 to 1922 by A. R. Orage, those writing for the *New Age* included G. B. Shaw, H. G. Wells, G. K. Chesterton, H. Belloc, Wyndham Lewis, Ezra Pound, J. Pentz and T. E. Hulme, among others. The then correspondent, José Pla, who considered Maeztu his “friend and teacher”,¹⁷ weighed up the importance of the movement: “Many of their propositions, sharply combated when expounded for the first time, now form part of, in a more or less attenuated form, the program of the ‘Trade Unions’, not only in England, but in the

The romantic man erred in considering himself—à la Rousseau—naturally good, capable of unlimited progress and perfectibility.

self-governing lands of the Empire as well.”¹⁸

As a reader of the magazine, Maeztu followed the controversy between Shaw and Wells, on the one hand, and the arguments of Belloc—“a brilliant and poor writer”—and Chesterton, “the best feature writer in the English press”, on the other.¹⁹ He was absorbing a new concept of the Middle Ages, together with a positive evaluation of Christian influence on society, present in Belloc’s works or in Chesterton’s *Orthodoxy* (1908). If Pentz showed him the pre-eminence of the spirit over the cult of machines, the writer who had most influence over Maeztu was the thinker Thomas Ernest Hulme.

Hulme—whose death in the Great War after being wounded and enlisting twice as a volunteer shook Maeztu—was a theorist of “Vorticism”, a friend of Bergson’s and

translator of G. Sorel’s *Réflexions sur la violence*. His prestige was to have an influence on personalities as diverse as T. S. Eliot and D. H. Lawrence. Hulme accused the Renaissance of losing the objectivity of values, and succumbing to the consequent ethical relativism. The romantic man, in turn, erred in considering himself—à la Rousseau—naturally good, capable of unlimited progress and perfectibility. In contrast to them, Hulme proclaimed the objectivity of values germane to the medieval world—not its political framework, for which this English writer preferred Sorel—and the recognition of man’s imperfection *ab origine*.

The idea of original sin had already been addressed by other writers in the *New Age*. The first mention is by Chesterton, in 1912: “Christianity believes in Original Sin: so do I: so does the ‘man in the street’. It is the only quite self-evident truth in Christianity.”²⁰ Maeztu assumed such thinking joyfully, and it was to form part of the core of his *Authority, Liberty and Function in the Light of War* (1916), the Spanish version of which appeared in 1919 as *La crisis del humanismo*. The theological principle of the Fall would become the anthropological key to unravel the history of European thought and to outline a project for a future society.

The doctrine of original sin—today at best provocative—does not refer to a hereditary personal fault, but to a disturbance of human nature, thus circumventing both Lutheran pessimism—which believes human nature to be rotten to the core—and the ingenuity of *l’homme naturel*, which does not satisfactorily elucidate the obvious presence of evil within the person. Pascal, noticing the persistent human search for the truth and happiness, which splinters in the face of uncertainty and death, concludes: “Ce désir nous est laissé tant pour nous punir que pour nous faire sentir d’où nous sommes tombés.”²¹ George Steiner, speaking at the Sorbonne upon the deficiencies of the ideal of the Enlightenment, asserted:

[Joseph de Maistre] understood something fundamental: The Enlightenment is essentially the intended and

conscious attempt to overturn the reality of original sin, to deny the Fall. That is why all criticism of the Enlightenment must try to restore the notion of original fall. . . . What should we say today? How should we teach? How can we bring to people's attention that material success is not man's goal, that California is not Paradise? . . . The *felix culpa* should be taught.²²

Authority, Liberty and Function in the Light of War, published the year of Maeztu's conversion, was received with enthusiasm in the guild movement for endeavoring to achieve theoretical systematization (through the concept of the "function", a proposal of values and the use of L. Duguit's "objective law") and the development that this entailed. Beyond its influence on British

trade unionism we must emphasize Maeztu's conversion and his concern with the "death-resurrection" principle in the life of the Christian: "The doctrine of the death and resurrection makes way for man's obedience to superior things."²³

As Sobejano well summarizes, "in [Maeztu's] first [stage] the will (to power) dominates; in the second, the intellect (the inquiry into ideas in the service of knowledge), and in the last the religious spirit (religiousness, love)."²⁴ His life journey, truncated in 1936, when he was murdered in Republican-controlled Madrid, contained abundant achievements and mistakes. He was characterized by a truthful and passionate temperament that, as with so many intellectuals of his generation, contended with the breakdown of modernity, both in the political field—the collapse of democracies—and in the cultural one, in which the crisis of values led many down the road to relativism and even to the black hole of nihilism.

His "regenerationism" and nationalism were rooted in Christian theology and subject to it: "God is the guarantor of man's true development, inasmuch as, having created him in his image, he also establishes the transcendent dignity of men and women and feeds their innate yearning to 'be more'."²⁵ That will to power, inherent in man, is commendable if, instead of setting it up against others and the Other, it is devoted to personal improvement, here and now—a fulfillment of man that, filtered through love, will diffuse good in abundance for others.

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